

HarvREST
Greener Farming with RES

D8.12

Project website

26 / 03 / 2024

Funded by
the European Union

www.harvrest.eu

PROJECT INFORMATION

ACRONYM	HarvRESt
PROJECT NAME	Harnessing the vast potential of RES for sustainable farming
PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-7
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
PROJECT NUMBER	101136904
START DAY	1 January 2024
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	D8.12 Project website
WORK PACKAGE	WP8
TASK	Task 8.2
LEAD PARTNER	Laila Dam (FBCD)
CONTRIBUTORS	All partners
DATE	26 / 03 / 2024
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	CHANGES	RESPONSIBLE PARTNER
0.1	06/03/2024	First draft sent to all partners	FBCD
0.2	22/03/2024	Revision to V0.1	All partners
0.3	26/03/2024	Final version adapted according to partner input	FBCD
1.0	26/03/2024	Final version submitted to EC	CIRCE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
2.	STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE.....	6
3.	WEBSITE CONTENT	7
4.	ANNEXES	9
4.1	Annex 1 Screenshots of the HarvRESt website	9

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In March 2024 (month 3) the project website www.harvrest.eu has been launched according to plan. FBCD has developed the website and is also in charge of its regular update as well as of its overall visual identity.

The aim of the website is to disseminate the project details and results to a wider audience. The website provides information about the project including objectives, links to related sites, materials developed and information on exploitable results for industry and investors and will promote upcoming project events. It will also represent a one-stop source for information for exploitable opportunities. The website will be updated throughout the project lifetime as results emerge, additional materials are developed, and relevant news arise.

2. STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The HarvREST project website www.harvrest.eu has many purposes as it should address all target groups of the project including agricultural communities and relevant associations, investors and agro-entrepreneurs, energy players and technology providers, policymakers, and the public. To accommodate all target groups the website is currently structured as illustrated in Figure 1.

As results emerge, new sections to the website could be anticipated. For example, a “Tools” section from which some of the tools that are going to be developed within HarvREST could be showed.

Figure 1. website structure

The website is designed in line with the HarvREST design guide to ensure recognisability and has user-friendly navigation. Further, the website is designed in a responsive design, which means that the layout of the webpage is adjusted and adapted to any screen size, whether using, for example a PC, a phone or a tablet.

3. WEBSITE CONTENT

The different sections on the website contain the following content:

- **HOME**

The home section provides a brief introduction to the project, including why the project has been launched and what the purpose of the project is, expected outcomes, the benefits of integrating RES at a farm level, links to use cases and “HarvRESt in numbers”. Further, the home section also offers an overview of the partners behind the project and shows the latest news from the project. The option to join the newsletter is also available.

- **ABOUT**

The “About” section contains three subsections 1) “The project”, which provides a more in-depth introduction to the HarvRESt project including project objectives, approach, expected results, expected impacts, link to use cases; 2) “Project partners”, which gives an overview of the partners involved in the project as well as a short description of them and links to their respective websites; 3) “Related initiatives”, where a list of selected related projects is provided along with a description and links to the project websites.

- **NEWS & EVENTS**

This section will showcase the project’s latest news, events and progress as we move forward. Examples of news items could be press releases issued in the project, key take-aways from events, promotion of public deliverable reports, how to get engaged in the project, etc. The section will also include an encouragement to sign up for the project's newsletter.

- **USE CASES**

In this section a brief introduction to the 4 use cases is provided including partners involved, and the key objectives.

- **RESULTS & PUBLICATIONS**

The “Results & publications” section is intended for different kinds of documents produced in the project and will be the main repository of information on results. The section will among others include a press kit (HarvRESt logo, HarvRESt visual identity guidelines, free images), communication materials (roll-up, poster, leaflet, etc.) HarvRESt newsletters, press releases and reports including public deliverables.

- **CONTACT**

In the contact section information on how to get in touch with the project coordinator, project manager and the dissemination & communication manager is provided. Further, a link to the “Project partners” section is provided, so that the visitor can find more information about the partners involved.

- **FOOTER**

The footer contains the EU logo as well as a funding acknowledgement and a disclaimer text so that this information is always accessible wherever you move around on the website. A link to the Privacy Policy page has been added to the footer, which also includes a link to our cookie policy so that users of the website can learn about how their data is being managed. Further, links to HarvRESt’s profile

on LinkedIn and X are displayed so that people easily can follow the project on these platforms. Finally, a link to the HarvRESt newsletter sign-up form is provided.

4. ANNEXES

4.1 Annex 1 Screenshots of the HarvRESt website

The screenshot shows the HarvRESt website homepage. At the top left is the HarvRESt logo with the tagline 'Greener Farming with RES'. To the right is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'News', 'Use cases', 'Results & publications', and 'Contact'. The main heading reads 'Enhancing the sustainable production of renewable energy on farms'. Below this is a paragraph explaining the project's goal: 'About 30% of the world's energy is consumed within agri-food systems and about a quarter of the total energy is consumed during the production stage, being responsible for a third of agri-food systems' emissions of greenhouse gases. There is therefore a need to reduce the impact of energy consumption in this sector. For this purpose, HarvRESt has been launched with the aim of vertically integrating Renewable Energy Sources (RES) into farms by improving the existing knowledge of options for reducing carbon emissions on farms.' Two buttons, 'Learn more' and 'Contact us', are provided. On the right, a large image shows solar panels installed in a field. Below the text, three statistics are displayed: '4 use cases will provide data', '200 agricultural & energy stakeholders will be involved', and '1500+ Farms will be reached'.

The screenshot shows the footer of the HarvRESt website. It features the HarvRESt logo and tagline on the left. In the center, there is a 'Join our newsletter' button. On the right, there are social media icons for X and LinkedIn, with the text 'Follow us:'. Below the logo, there is a 'Funded by the European Union' logo and a disclaimer: 'Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.' At the bottom center, the copyright notice reads: '© Copyright 2024 | HarvRESt | All Rights Reserved | Data Policy'.

Latest news

14 March 2024

Pioneering a Sustainable Future for European Agriculture through Innovative RES Integration

New EU-funded project aims to enhance the sustainable production of renewable energy at farm-level.

[Read More](#)

31 January 2024

The HarvREST project is off to a good start

On 30-31 January 2024 the HarvREST partners met for a kick-off meeting in Zaragoza, Spain

[Read More](#)

Main outcomes of HarvREST

To support the uptake and upscaling of RES production on farms HarvREST will develop:

An Agricultural Virtual Power Plant (AVPP)

Capable of running diverse scenarios and farm configurations. The tool will determine the best operational procedures for a given RES solution.

[More about HarvREST](#)

A Decision Support System (DSS)

To make recommendations of the best RES integration solutions & operation procedures for optimized production based on data from the AVPP.

[More about HarvREST](#)

A Business Model Catalogue

Containing relevant innovative business models, considering financial schemes and incentives while identifying risks.

[More about HarvREST](#)

WHY HARVREST?

The HarvREST project has been launched to address the need of enhancing the use of renewable energy technologies (RES) along with sustainable farming methods, aiming to help the agricultural and food industry reduce carbon emissions.

However, deciding how best to integrate green energy on a farm is not without its challenges. The decision is a complex one, with many factors to be taken into account. HarvREST will therefore work on solutions that alleviate this challenge.

OUR MAIN OBJECTIVE

More knowledge for better decisions

The main objective of HarvREST is to improve the existing knowledge of options for reducing carbon emissions on farms, by maximising synergies between the integration of RES and sustainable agricultural practices. This will result in a decision support system capable of providing ad-hoc recommendations to both farmers and policy makers that will make it possible to achieve improved production rates on renewable energy as well as food & feed, within agricultural communities.

Related initiatives

HarvREST relies on the lessons from previous EU and national projects addressing bioeconomy strategies and implementation of novel renewable energy sources.

Below you can find information on some of these relevant projects.

Wendy

The main objective of the Wendy project is to trigger a change in the social perception of onshore and offshore wind energy projects. To unravel the triggers for social acceptance of wind farms, a multi-spatial planning and impact assessment tool will be developed and validated through a comprehensive social, environmental and technical analysis.

[Visit website](#)

ALFA

ALFA will foster the market uptake of biogas production technologies that use manure as biomass (either within livestock farms or in biogas plants), thus helping increase the production of renewable energy in the EU and helping reduce emissions from untreated livestock farming waste.

[Visit website](#)

[Press kit](#)

[Communication materials](#)

[Press releases](#)

[Newsletters](#)

[Reports](#)

Press kit

HarvREST Visual Identity Guidelines

[Download](#)

HarvREST logo

[Download](#)

Copyright free images

[Download](#)

The project

The HarvREST project aims to enhance the sustainable production of renewable energy at farm-level. This approach not only makes farms climate-neutral but also optimizes production, reduces their impact on natural resources and biodiversity, and provides energy services to communities, thereby diversifying economic income. However, deciding how best to integrate renewable energy sources (RES) on a farm is not without its challenges. The decision is a complex one, with many factors to consider. Due to this, HarvREST seeks to identify, understand, and overcome the existing barriers hindering the widespread adoption of this innovative approach. Current initiatives often overlook the complex interactions and factors within the farming and RES context, resulting in ineffective support for decision-making based on accurate projections, estimations, and forecasts. HarvREST will therefore consolidate and enhance existing knowledge, creating an Agricultural Virtual Power Plant capable of running diverse scenarios and farm configurations. This tool will determine the best operational procedures for a given RES solution, providing valuable data to a decision support system. This system will weigh trade-offs and key indicators, offering tailor-made recommendations to farmers and policymakers.

PARTNER		SHORT NAME
	CIRCE Research Centre	CIRCE
	BETA Technological Centre	UVic-UCC
	NORCE	NORCE
	Tecnolimenti	TCA
	WHITE	WR
	Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions Ltd.	Suite5
	EnGreen	EnG
	ConTerra	CT

Confagricoltura	Confagricoltura	CONFAGRI
	Fattoria Solidale del Circeo	FSDC
	Viñas del Vero	VdV
	Viñedos del Rio Tajo	VRT
	Sorigué	ACSA
	Grønn Gårdsenergi AS	GGE
	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark	FBCD
	EIT Climate-KIC	CKIC

Contact us

www.harvrest.eu

 <https://linkedin.com/harvREST>

 https://twitter.com/HarvRESt_eu